

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

MAP Position Paper

TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE & RESILIENT VALUE CHAINS

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<https://rural-interfaces.eu/maps/france-pays-pyrenees-mediterranee/>

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1. Objectives of the SHERPA PPM platform and work organisation

During the third phase of the SHERPA project, the work of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée (PPM) platform falls within the framework of the SHERPA's topic on "Entrepreneurship, social economy, just transition and resilient value chains".

The specific objective of the SHERPA Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) of PPM was to **put into perspective the territorial food project (TFP) of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée as a smart tool for territorial transition** within the framework of the EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas and the regional programming of European funds, in a context marked in particular by:

- Climate crisis and its effects on an already heavily impacted rural area;
- New societal demands for healthier and more environmentally friendly agriculture, fishing and food products;
- The effects of the pandemic and the war in Ukraine on food markets, especially for energy, raw materials and agricultural commodities.

The SHERPA MAP aimed to accompany the PPM initiative, as the TFP is emerging:

- To clarifying some of the issues and objectives of the TFP in the context mentioned above and in the light of the objectives of the European Commission's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (first workshop of the MAP);
- To come up with public policy proposals for rural areas, in particular those of the European Union, which enable the TFP to respond to the issues and challenges identified.

In addition to the creation of the SHERPA MAP led by the CIHEAM with the support of the LAG Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée, the SHERPA MAP issued:

- A discussion paper that outlines the main key issues for the TFP in a long-term vision of the PPM's rural territories, taking into account the international and local context in which it is set (Summer 2022);
- This position paper summarising the main elements contained in the first report and proposes public policy recommendations, particularly at EU level, concerning the implementation of a TFP as a smart tool for territorial transitions.

2. The general and local context of the TFP

The context in which the TFP was set up (see Working Document and Annex 1 of the Working Document: some data on the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée) is marked by:

2.1. Climate change and its effects on rural areas

The Pyrénées-Orientales department, to which the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée belongs to, is recognised by scientists as one of the departments in mainland France that is most vulnerable to climate change (ECTAdapt project).

The effects of climate change are already present and are expected to increase in the medium and long term in this department. These are: rise in temperatures with more frequent and intense heat periods and less frequent cold extremes; drop in annual rainfall totals and change in their rainfall distribution with more severe

and more frequent droughts; increase in the frequency and intensity of natural hazards (flooding, fire, marine submersion, etc.).

Rural territories, economic activities and population of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée will be increasingly affected by the following changes¹: shortage of water resources; modification of agricultural yields and drop in productivity; impacts on seafood resources and therefore fishing activities; modification of ecosystems and significant impacts on bio-diversity and forests; questioning of the winter tourism model of the medium and high mountain resorts and evolution of the coastline.

The agricultural sector accounts for a large share of greenhouse gas emissions. Therefore, its adaptation is important to fight against the effects of climate change on food and agricultural production. It is also an important sector in terms of climate mitigation (e.g. carbon sinks, bioenergy production).

It should be noted that the PPM has therefore launched a TACCT approach², in order to develop a policy for adaptation to climate change from "A to Z", from the vulnerability diagnosis to the monitoring of measures and the evaluation of the strategy.

2.2. Effects of health crisis on the food chain and new societal demands

"The COVID-19 pandemic has underlined the importance of a strong and resilient food system that functions under all circumstances and is able to provide citizens with sufficient food at affordable prices. It also made us particularly aware of the interrelationships between our health, our ecosystems, our supply chains, our consumption patterns and our global limits. It is clear that we need to do much more to keep ourselves and our planet healthy. The current pandemic is just one example. Increasing droughts, floods, forest fires and new pests are constant reminders that our food system is under threat and needs to become more sustainable and resilient"³.

The National Food Council (CNA), in its opinion 89, notes⁴ that the COVID-19 crisis and its management (containment) had significant effects on the French food system, which had to adapt to it. Consequently to the lifting of the containment, some of these effects have disappeared or became less significant, and the adaptation measures have sometimes fizzled out, whereas others have persisted.

The health crisis has accentuated the development of alternative distribution systems and short circuits. In practice, what has happened is: the multiplication of local and solidarity-based initiatives for the sale of products and direct contact between producers and consumers (farm drives, platforms, click and collect, online sales, etc.); the raise of collective approaches (pooling of distribution and delivery methods, farmers' groups, etc.); the establishment of collaborations with large-scale distributors for the sale of products that cannot be sold in their usual sales channels (referencing of local producers, promotion of festive products, highlighting of products that are not sold in their usual channels, etc.). In addition, solidarity initiatives (donations to food aid associations, hospital staff, mutual aid between neighbours, etc.) and self-production (gardening and vegetable gardening and an increase in the practice of "homemade") have further developed.

These developments respond to new societal demands for healthier and more environmentally friendly agriculture, fisheries and food: relocation of production and short circuits, quality products and healthier food, fair prices, products that respect the environment and animal welfare, lower meat consumption, limiting food waste, etc.

¹ From: <https://www.ectadapt.eu/fr/ce-qui-ete-fait-jusqua-present/le-departement-des-pyrenees-orientales>

² TACCT (Trajectoires d'Adaptation au Changement Climatique des Territoires). ADEME provides a methodological guide and a computer tool <https://tacct.ademe.fr>

³ European Commission, A Farm to Fork Strategy for a Fair, Healthy and Environmentally Sound Food System, COM (2020) 381 final, 20/05/2020

⁴ NAC, Feedback from the COVID 19 crisis, Opinion 89

Moreover, food insecurity exploded during the containment and has remained high since. It is now affecting new groups, such as students, partially unemployed people, self-employed people and so on. Social structures and solidarity associations are finding it increasingly difficult to respond to this influx of demand, while the supply of available products has tended to decrease (CNA, Avis n°89).

2.3. Growing uncertainties about international market developments accentuated by the war in Ukraine

The war in Ukraine is already having a significant impact on international agricultural markets. Russia and Ukraine account for 30% of the world's wheat and barley exports. Ukraine is also the world's 4th largest exporter of maize and holds dominant positions on the world sunflower market, i.e. in oil, but also in oilcake, increasing the cost of animal feed. With the Russian invasion, Ukrainian ports have been blocked and exports paralysed or severely slowed down. As a result, wheat prices have soared by 40% since the beginning of the war on the European market (Euronext), with a tonne currently trading at € 400.

Rising energy prices have led to a sharp increase in the price of fertilisers, some of which are imported from Russia or Belarus. Increasing price of energy is also having an impact on marketing and production costs along the food value chain.

The war in Ukraine is therefore jeopardising both the supply and food security of major cereal and oilseed importing countries (particularly in the southern Mediterranean and sub-Saharan Africa), destabilising international markets for agricultural products and leading to an increase in the production costs of agricultural products in the region (fertilisers, energy and livestock feed). It also calls into question current agricultural policy, both in terms of regulating agricultural markets, which allow for a certain degree of food sovereignty, and in terms of production methods (less dependent on the outside). At the local level, the effects of this war justify the trend towards a relocation of production, the development of short circuits and a more resilient agriculture less dependent on imported inputs.

2.4. Evolution and challenges of the agricultural sector

The agricultural sector is key for the rural economy of the PPM, but also in terms of land use planning and environmental and natural resource management.

As in the rest of the country, this sector is faced with numerous challenges that are becoming increasingly significant: decrease in the number of farms; ageing of farmers; difficulties of installation due to strong pressure on agricultural land; increasing climatic constraint; deregulation of agricultural markets; weak market power of farmers in the value chains and their low remuneration; lack of agricultural labour and the social management of "imported" labour; evolution of practices to adapt to new societal expectations in terms of healthy food, but also respect for the environment; relocation of production, development of short and local circuits and the promotion of local quality products.

2.5. Trends and challenges of the fisheries sector

The fishing sector is an important sector for the economy of the region and especially for the PPM. In 2021, this sector will account for 8,000 direct and indirect jobs, and generate more than € 137 million in turnover (CESER).

This sector faces numerous challenges, notably: pollution of the Mediterranean sea, decrease of fish population and of fishing areas, and different constraints linked to European regulations (reduction of days at sea, periodicity, net size, etc.). The rise in fuel prices is also an essential aspect that further weakens the balance of the farms. Furthermore, the fishing sector, including shellfish farming (in addition to health

problems with virus and bacterial contamination), is facing the growing effects of global warming, which will require strong adaptations.

3. The TFP of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée: an institutional territorial framework visioning towards a fair and sustainable food system

Territorial food projects (TFPs) aim to support the territorial relocalisation of agriculture and food by supporting the setting up of farmers, short supply chains or local food products in canteens. Emerged as a result of the Law on the Future of Agriculture, which has encouraged their development since 2014, they are drawn up collectively on the initiative of territorial actors (e.g. local authorities, agricultural and agri-food companies, craftsmen, citizens).

The general challenge imposed on the TFP is: how to combine food relocation, transition and resilience? For instance, how to relocate food in order to reconstitute a food ecosystem that enhances the resources of the territory by allowing access for all to healthy food produced in a sustainable manner?

Exchanges with the different actors involved have evidenced the following main thematic issues of the TFP:

- Preservation and reclamation of agricultural land and sustainable management of water resources;
- Accelerating the process of agroecological transition (living soils, legume production, etc.) by adapting to climate change;
- Improving the network and structuring the entire food value chain, from production to processing and marketing (short supply chains), so that it is more organic, local and accessible;
- The implementation of the TFP's ambitions through more local and accessible collective catering, promoting health and education (quality food, increasing the share of plant proteins, combating waste, etc.) and enhancing the culinary heritage;
- The mobilisation and involvement of associations and citizens to carry out inclusive, educational and intergenerational projects and to promote the link between health and food.

Based on a census of projects and consultation with territorial stakeholders, several thematic working groups called "poles" were set up. Their role is to enable stakeholders to reflect and develop a strategy and an action plan for each theme. The topics discussed are not exhaustive and to date five topics have been identified as priorities. They have two objectives: Preparing food resilience and agroecological transition and Integrating people and making food a vector of social progress

Objective 1: Preparing for food resilience and agroecological transition

- **Agricultural Land and Water Management Unit**

Land is a fundamental element because it is necessary to have agricultural land to install new producers. Although our territory has very diversified production, the volume produced does not cover all of the population's need for food (cf. CRATER source). Several levers will be mobilised: reclaiming wasteland, PAEN, land consolidation, etc.

- **Agroecological Transition Cluster**

The aim is to accompany the actors of the territory in this approach; to understand and define an agroecology adapted to this territory; to improve knowledge based on local examples; to network producers with training and research structures in order to share the various added values of agroecology; to raise awareness among new audiences; to inform and mobilise consumers; to improve and regenerate biodiversity (rehabilitation, planting of hedges, living soil, etc.).

- **Catering/Supply Chain/Retail**

The aim here is to support the actors who request it; encourage networking to facilitate the construction of projects; promote local examples; promote the objectives of the EGALIM law; support the supply network, in synergy with the departmental TFP platform.

Objective 2: Integrate people and make food a vehicle for social progress

- **Integration Workshops and community gardens**

The aim is to bring together the actors involved in integration initiatives in order to discuss the levers and share the tools for transmitting food know-how and life skills, with the aim of enabling everyone to take ownership of the food issues and preventing food from becoming a factor of marginalisation. This group also enables us to work on social links and the cross-cutting nature of the public around the shared garden project.

- **Health and Food Education Unit**

It is a question of promoting the link between health and food by relying on local initiatives, such as the Local Health Contract, by also carrying out actions aimed at young and not so young people and families, and by relying on regional strategies such as the Plant Protein Plan or the National Health and Food Strategy.

We should also note the setting up of **a think tank for cross-border exchanges**. This is an action that aims to exchange on the TFP approaches of neighbouring territories, particularly within the framework of the EU Green Deal, resilient and virtuous food and the Catalonia Food Project. It can allow specific actions to emerge, for instance, the continuation of the ALBERAPASTUR project, on the development of local breeds and the management of pastures or the promotion of Catalan culinary heritage, such as the Catalan gastronomic routes.

Finally, a **research group** has been set up. It is made up of several structures from fundamental and applied research, and its role is to bring out applied research work or tutored projects.

4. The TFP of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée: a smart tool for agricultural and food transitions in rural areas and for territorial cooperation

4.1. The PPM TFP, a smart tool for agricultural and food transition in rural areas

During the first workshop, after having exchanged on the context, it was proposed to the participants to select (choose 3) and prioritise the structuring factors of the European Commission's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (LTVRA) (EC, 2021), which would enable development of a sustainable and resilient food system for rural territories. In a second step, we have verified that these determining factors correspond well or partially to the main issues and priority themes of the current TFP.

During the second workshop, participants were asked to *"show how the achievements and field projects supported by the TFP help to support agricultural and food transitions in rural areas"*.

Prioritisation of determining factors

The difficulty of prioritising the determining factors was underlined as they are interdependent and complementary (cf. the three types of resilience). Moreover, some factors are quite similar or even overlapping (e.g. social innovation/social resilience). It is therefore important to have a global approach

which takes into account the interdependencies and interconnections between the different factors. Similarly, the distinction between environmental resilience and climate resilience is not self-evident. In the light of these remarks, the priority determining factors cited by the participants are the following:

Sustainable food production (1st priority)

For the implementation of a TFP, it is obviously logical to retain this determining factor, as sustainable food production is at the centre of a coherent and resilient food system. It is about building a resilient ecosystem and educating people to this vision. To be sustainable, food production must be remunerative throughout the food chain and allow food to be accessible to all consumers. It is also linked to the prosperity of rural areas. It is an environmentally, socially and economically sustainable production.

Some of the participants specifically mentioned:

- Respect for people, land, the environment and water resources;
- Strengthening of measures allowing access to and protection of agricultural land;
- The development of short supply chains and therefore the reduction of mobility (link with the climate and resilience law);
- The development of agro-ecology and soil carbon capture;
- The development of new productions (adaptation) and the development of organic and local collective catering;
- Local farmers' seed production ;
- The link to environmental resilience and watershed management;
- The need to evaluate the effects of the CAP reform and the impact of the development of short supply chains on the transport of food products (food miles/volume transported).

Social resilience (2nd priority) and social innovation (4th priority)

The two concepts are seen as close and very much linked. Their choice underlines the importance of the human element in TFP and the notions of equality and inclusion.

For many participants, the aim of the TFP is to provide access for all, and in particular the most vulnerable and isolated, to healthy, quality food (fight against inequalities), with a particular focus on canteens and the fight against food waste.

It was also mentioned that it is important to work on the distribution of territories and productions and to determine the capacities of reception of populations and activities, in connection with the generated needs.

More globally, it is a societal dynamic that aims to fight against inequalities and promote a better distribution of wealth. The aim is to work together to find collective solutions and create social innovations.

One participant also stressed the need for environmental education and personal development (alternative education).

Social innovations are jobs to be created that do not exist, particularly in agriculture or in the SSE, in connection with a sustainable food system (see also diversification of activities)

Climate change resilience (3^d priority)

This was the third determining factor chosen by participants in the workshop. The choice reflects a clear awareness of the need to consider climate change's effects on food production (agricultural or fisheries). Participants emphasised: good management of water resources, preservation of natural resources,

development of green spaces, reduction of distribution channels, carbon neutrality and development of the circular economy.

A resilient food system is one that does not increase GHG emissions (sobriety/adaptation) and contributes to their reduction (mitigation).

A link was also made with urban planning tools and therefore the preservation of agricultural areas. In the same vein, it was proposed to study the agronomic quality of soils and water resources to guide land use planning documents at municipality level, particularly in the context of the implementation of the objective of zero net urban sprawling by 2050. It should be noted that this is part of the research scope of the European Commission's Rural Action Plan.

Diversification of economic activities (other priority)

This is one of the challenges of the relocation of production, but also of the attractiveness of rural areas. It is a question of developing new remunerative productions that must be sober, including in terms of land and energy use (see also social innovations).

For one of the speakers, it is a question of encouraging the installation of small local farmers as close as possible to consumers, diversifying production, relocating processing and increasing the number of sales outlets.

Access to services (other priority)

Access to services, especially education and health, is essential to prevent rural areas from becoming empty and to make them attractive again.

Digital connectivity (other priority)

Good digital connectivity promotes access to services and the attractiveness of rural areas. It is also a question of promoting links and interactions between the various actors in society.

Transport/Mobility (other priority)

The lack of public transport connections (bus, regional trains, taxis on demand, etc.) and poor development of carpooling in rural areas of the PPM were highlighted.

It is therefore a question of rethinking mobility in relation to sobriety (fewer journeys, less use of the car) and of having a new relationship with time planning. It is also about desilting and renaturing urban spaces to fight against the effects of climate change.

Environmental resilience (other priority)

Environmental resilience is quite similar to climate resilience. The participants mentioned in particular the development of environmentally friendly activities and the circular economy (e.g. reuse of glass jars and bottles).

Carbon neutrality and good management of natural resources, especially water, were also mentioned.

How do the achievements and field projects supported by the TFP make it possible to support agricultural and food transitions in rural areas?

The elements presented in the above sections already provide evidence to this question. Indeed, they show the coherence of the FTP projects and priorities with the European Commission's Long-Term Vision for rural areas. The exchanges occurred during the second workshop complement and reinforce this analysis:

- It was first called that the TFP is part of the 2021-2027 strategy of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée⁵ which is based on five fundamental principles against which each action is systematically examined. Four of these principles contribute to the objective of agricultural and food transition:
 - Principle 1: A more sober territory
 - Principle 2: An inclusive territory that listens to people
 - Principle 3: A territory that is more respectful of the living world
 - Principle 4: A resilient territory

These principles are thus selection criteria for the different actions developed in the TFP.

The Pays is in fact a local development tool that mobilises its own or external engineering to identify innovative new projects that respond, on the basis of the principles mentioned above, to the various challenges facing rural areas.

- Beyond the principles mentioned above, the transition approach is thus at the heart of the TFP, which aims to meet the following general challenge: How to combine relocation, transition and resilience?
- To promote this agricultural and food transition and to accompany changes in production and consumption patterns, the TFP of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée mobilises three levels of organisation:
 - The identification of "innovation niches" in the territory;
 - In order to evolve and develop, rural areas, which do not have all the services and resources available to urban areas, must innovate and experiment;
 - A system of territorial governance associating all the actors concerned (researchers, public decision-makers, private and associative sectors, citizens) and encouraging networking;
 - In this governance system, researchers have a role as observers, collectors of innovations, disseminators and transferers of knowledge and good practices. They provide advice throughout the governance process; however, the decision-making process concerning the projects to be implemented depends on a public-private partnership;
 - The implementation of concrete actions on the territory, in particular by disseminating or reproducing the innovations identified (change of scale).

The TFP articulates these three levels of organisation, with the aim of supporting the transition through technical, organisational or institutional innovation. In itself, the approach, like the SHERPA MAP, is an innovative approach/institutional innovation.

- The TFP is a catalyst for projects and innovations, but it also aims to disseminate and sustain these innovations.
- A **research group** has been set up to bring out innovations and linking together several structures from fundamental and applied research. The aim is to decompartmentalise the players and to rely on collective intelligence and networking.
- As mentioned in the previous points and thanks to the selection criteria, the different projects supported by the TFP contribute (or will contribute) to the agricultural, fisheries and food transitions of the PPM, as follows:

⁵ Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée, Strategy 2021-2027 (payspyreneesmediterranee.org)

- Land division deals with a major aspect of agricultural transition and is led by the chamber of agriculture of Pyrénées Orientales with Terres de Liens NGO;
- Ecological transition cluster promotes the development of agro-ecology;
- the collective catering unit is working on the issue of school canteens and the promotion of local production;
- Integration projects and shared gardens division carries out integration and awareness-raising initiatives on food issues;
- Health-food cluster promotes the links between food and health by building on local initiatives.

4.2. The TFP as a tool for cooperation between territories

The fifth principle of the strategy of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée is "a territory that cooperates". Cooperation is therefore also an important point of the TFP.

On the one hand, the production of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée is far from covering the total territorial demand for food. PPM depends on the outside world for many products (see Annex 1 Working document), and part of the production is exported outside its territory. It is therefore necessary to consider supplies beyond PPM territory, distinguishing between exchanges of products with more or less nearby territories (Occitany's neighbouring departments and in the Southern region, and even in other French regions, in Catalonia and internationally).

On the other hand, the PPM, in terms of agriculture, fishing and food, shares common problems with many other rural territories neighbouring the Department or the Region, or even further afield (Southern Region, Catalonia...). In fact, there are many TFP experiences in the department of the Pyrénées Orientales and more generally in the Occitanie region and in neighbouring rural areas (particularly in the Southern Region). These are all possibilities for exchanging experiences to be developed and capitalised on.

Thus, the PPM's TFP :

- Has a think tank working on cross-border exchanges with the aim of pooling the various TFP approaches and cooperation with neighbouring territories;
- Is part of the network of TFPs in the Eastern Pyrenees and participates in the Plateforme "Mangeons local 66", the territorial project for the Eastern Pyrenees⁶;
- Cooperates with the other TFPs in the region through the regional network of TFPs⁷ led by the DRAAF Occitanie. Today, 51 territorial food projects (TFPs) have been labelled in the region. Support for the implementation of the TFPs, which creates a real synergy between the various TFPs in the region, is part of the Regional Food Plan (RFP) in Occitany. This latter one is the regional version of the National Food Plan;
- Benefits from the experiences of other TFPs on the national territory through the national network of RnPATs⁸;
- Developed connections with the TFP of Ariège Department;
- Developed exchanges of experiences and joint reflections with the TFP of the Generalidad de Catalunya.

⁶ [Mangeons Local 66 : a Territorial Food Project for the Pyrénées-Orientales. - Chambre d'agriculture Pyrénées-Orientales - Chamber of Agriculture of the Pyrénées-Orientales \(chambre-agriculture.fr\)](#)

⁷ [Territorial food projects \(TFP\) - DRAAF Occitanie \(agriculture.gouv.fr\)](#)

⁸ [RNPAT - National Network for a co-constructed and shared territorial food project](#)

5. Main recommendations of the SHERPA Platform for regional, national and European decision-makers

First of all, the TFPs, as their name tells, are territorialised. TFPs are cross-cutting projects and this feature allows FTP projects to question all of issues related to sustainable food systems. FTPs are schemes which, like LEADER projects, allow to identify technical or organisational innovations. Today, this is a French specificity and it does not exist elsewhere in the European Union.

The first recommendation of the SHERPA PPM platform is therefore to have this smart tool to be recognised and promoted at European level as a tool for supporting agricultural and food transitions in rural areas.

The TFP is a cross-cutting tool that makes it possible to go beyond sectoral approaches and respond to the territorial challenges of food systems. At the European level, it is therefore an instrument that is fully in line with the European Commission's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas and it goes beyond the farmers-driven and sectoral interventions of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). It is a tool that enables synergies between territories, local policymakers and the food sectors.

The second recommendation is to promote TFPs through the CAP by securing a 5% envelope in the EAFRD regulation to support their implementation in rural territories. In doing so, the EAFRD would create an enabling environment for local-based food systems in rural areas.

The third recommendation is to "reward" virtuous territories that set up a TFP, for example by developing a label or a TFP bonus financed under the second pillar of the CAP.

Finally, a transition of rural territories towards more sustainable agriculture and food implies the promotion of more resilient modes of production that better respect the environment and that allow a fair and equitable remuneration of farmers and fishermen, while offering quality products at a price accessible to all consumers. **For the members of the SHERPA PPM platform, this implies significant changes to the CAP, in particular through aid linked to the number of workers employed and no longer to the surface area, and more substantial aid for production that respects the environment (organic farming, agro-ecology, etc.).** It is also a question of strengthening the negotiating power of farmers in the face of large-scale distribution and agri-foodstuffs and therefore of changing the methods of contractualisation.

Concerning the PPM's TFP itself, in addition to the proposal to progressively complete the themes covered (cf. previous point) and to eventually set up "cross-cutting clusters", for example on climate resilience, one recommendation would be to define the criteria for evaluating the projects supported by the TFP. This would contribute to the "good governance of the project". Here the experience of *Les greniers d'abondance*⁹, which through the CRATer project offers a digital tool to raise awareness and help diagnose the food resilience of territories, may be particularly useful (see Annex 1 of the Working Document).

⁹ CRATer: https://crater.resiliencealimentaire.org/diagnostic.html?idTerritoire=PAYS_PETR-OC07

Annexes

Annex 1 - List of SHERPA platform members

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Jean	LHERITIER	Président Slow food France	
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Géraldine	CAPRANI		
Caroline	BATAILLON		
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